

An Empirical Assessment of Dividend Pay-out on Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises in Kenya: Effects of the Bird in the Hand Theory

Author's Details:

Dr. Grace Akinyi Musa¹ Beatrice Kinanu Anyuki² Sandra Beldine Otieno³

^{1,2}Department of Accounting and Finance of the Technical University of Kenya.

³Data analyst; Data Coding, Analysis and Interpretation, Nairobi, Kenya.

Abstract

Research has shown that in making investment decisions, an investor is always required to accept a certain level of risk which is in line with the expected returns. A risk taker is an investor intrigued by the market volatility, viewing it as an opportunity to realize a higher return on their investments. An adverse risk investor prefers lower returns instead of higher ones because the lower returns have known risks unlike the higher returns which have higher risks. Risk neutral investors are those who are not sensitive to risks. These facts notwithstanding, research shows that most Micro and Small Enterprises have not been willing to undertake risks hence their investments in stock dividends have been minimal. This has been attributed to their fear of the future which is uncertain, and also due to negative perceptions developed by them towards engaging in any form of investment, including investing in stock dividends. The main objective of the study was an empirical assessment of the relationship between dividend payout and Growth of MSEs with effects of the 'Bird in The Hand' theory. The population of the study comprised of 100 Micro and Small Enterprises located within Nairobi's Central Business District in Kenya. The study applied a cross-sectional and ex-post facto research design. Data were analysed using logistic regression since the outcome of the study was binary and dichotomous in nature. Findings revealed a significant positive relationship between dividend payout and Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises in Kenya and a positive significant moderating effect of the 'Bird in the Hand' theory on the relationship between dividend payout and Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises in Kenya. The study recommended that for MSEs to facilitate their Growth, it was necessary that they invested in a stock paying dividends as proposed by the 'Bird in the Hand' dividend theory. The study has bridged the void created by prior studies which hitherto concentrated on other dividend theories including; the residual dividend theory, Modigliani and Miller dividend irrelevance theory and the tax preference theory.

Key Words: *Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises, the Bird in the Hand theory, Risk Averse Investor, Dividend Payout,*

Background

In Kenya, a baseline statistical national survey was conducted in 1999 where Small and Medium Enterprises (MSEs) was defined in various categories. Micro enterprises were defined as those enterprises having 1 up to 10 employees, small enterprises as those having 11 up to 50 employees and medium/large enterprises as those with more than 50 employees. Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs) are small in nature in terms of a number of employees, capital or asset turnover. MSEs Working capital and assets are limited and their overall turnover is usually small compared to larger enterprises (Mburu, 2012). It therefore follows that for MSEs to facilitate their Growth, investing in dividend stocks would be the best option. This is so because companies that pay Stock dividends are giving their shareholders the choice of keeping their profit or turning it to cash whenever they so desire and with a cash dividend, no other option is given (Pandey, 2015).

Due to these facts, it is expected that most MSEs would prefer to be paid their returns at the earliest opportunities possible. This is because they feel insecure with most of their monies tied up in capital which pays back after a long time. They would prefer to be paid even smaller incomes out of their investment 'now' than waiting for huge incomes out of long term capital gains in future. To ascertain the kind of risk investors MSEs belong, the current study decided to define the three types of risks investors which included; risk takers, risk averse and risk neutral. A risk taker is an investor who is intrigued from the market volatility, viewing it as an opportunity to realize a higher return on their investments. That is, they are ready to take higher risks with an expectation of higher returns. A risk averse investor is one who prefers lower returns instead of higher ones because the lower returns have known risks unlike the higher returns which

have higher risks. Risk neutral investors are those who are not sensitive to risks (Pandey, 2015). It is now clear from the definitions above that most MSEs fall under the category of risk averse investors.

It was further expected that MSEs, being risk averse investors, would have preferred companies whose dividends payout increased the companies' share prices. The consequence would be witnessed in a gain from the rise in form of higher dividends and selling the shares at higher profits. All these would be stronger indicators of stable MSEs which would translate into Growth. In addition, MSEs investors would prefer dividends from stock to potential capital gains. This would be due to the inherent uncertainty associated with capital gains given the instability in most MSEs. Hence the adage, 'a bird in the hand is worth two in the bush.' Capital gains investing represented 'the two in the bush' side of the adage. The 'Bird in The Hand' theory states that investors prefer the certainty of dividend payments to the possibility of substantially higher future capital gains (Pandey, 2015).

These facts notwithstanding, research has shown that most Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs) in many countries across the world still operate on 'a day at a time' and therefore have not embraced the importance of investing in dividend stocks. Further, prior studies have observed negative perceptions portrayed by most MSEs towards investment in dividends stocks. These were attributed to several factors including lack of business advisory services (Otengo, 2016), Low level of education amongst most MSEs (Otengo, 2016) and lack of adequate funds for investments.

The multiplier effects have been witnessed in the low Growth of MSEs in most countries globally. However, investment in dividend stocks has numerous advantages to MSEs investors. These include; Investment gains, Dividend Income and Diversification. It was expected that the advantages of investing in dividend stocks would enable MSEs make more profits which would accelerate the firms growth. This was due to the fact that stock paying dividends is usually reinvested back in the company or money given in form of cash at the request of the investors.

The multiplier effects would be experienced in the increase in a company's share prices, creation of more employment opportunities, increase in the standards of living of MSEs Employees and poverty reduction. This will not only increase MSEs performance but also improve the MSEs growth. Numerous studies have been conducted with regard to investments decisions without universal agreements. The studies concentrated mainly on Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) and Firms listed at other Stock exchanges including Nairobi Securities Exchange (NSE). Moreover, the studies focussed on other aspects ranging from financial, marketing, political - technological, location and social factors only (Malik, Khan & Rehman, 2019; Njuguna & Jagongo, 2015). The studies had different conceptual, contextual theoretical and methodological aspects from the current study. An empirical assessment of the relationship between dividend payout and Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises in Kenya with effects on the 'Bird in the Hand' theory was lacking.

Statement of the Problem: Research has shown that in making investment decisions, investors are always required to accept a certain level of risk which is in line with the expected returns (Finke, Huston, & Winchester, 2011). The main problem of the study was that most MSEs in most countries across the world had developed negative perceptions towards investing in dividend stocks. However, according to the 'Bird in the Hand' theory, one bird in the hand is worth two in the bush'. The implication is that companies that invest in stock dividends pay their investors in the form of stocks or cash at the investors' requests. However, these facts notwithstanding, research has shown that most MSEs lack adequate funds to facilitate investments (Miroslav and Aneta, 2017). They also lack business advisory services (Otengo, 2016) In addition, most of them have poor perceptions towards investments (Njuguna & Jagongo, 2015). These shortcomings could have negatively impacted on MSEs Profits since stocks paying dividends increases firms' earnings per share and value of the firms which eventually translates in to increased profit and hence the Growth of MSEs.

Numerous studies have been conducted on factors affecting investment decisions without a universal agreement. The studies focussed mainly on firms listed at the NSE with a concentration on value of share

prices, firms' liquidity position and cost of capital and sources of capital, only. A study by (Gveroski & Risteska, 2017) assessed the determinants of investment decisions in SMEs. The study established that liquidity of securities, problems related to the exact calculation of the cost of capital, and limited access to other sources of capital were the main determinants for impeding and complicating the process of evaluating the financial efficiency of investments by the SMEs.

A study by (Aroni, Namusonge, & Sakwa, 2014) examined the effect of dividend payout on investment in shares for Kenyan retail investors. The study applied the behavioural finance theory which states that investors or individuals rely on their emotions and psychological traits in making investment decisions.

Their findings meant that most investors did not consider the risk and return trade off of investment and past available information, which is the focus of the current study. Furthermore, Prior studies applied theories different from that used by the current study. Whereas the current study applied the 'Bird in the Hand' theory which informed the study's variables, prior studies applied mainly, the residual dividend theory, Modigliani and Miller dividend irrelevance theory and the tax preference theory. Research has also shown that past studies used other statistical models which included both co relational and regression models (Aroni, Namusonge, & Sakwa, 2014);(Njuguna & Jagongo, 2015). These were contrary to the current study which used a logistic regression model based on the binary dichotomous outcome.

From the discussions therein, it is evident that past studies created contextual, conceptual, theoretical and methodological gaps which the current study to fill up. The two big questions that the study sought to answer were: Firstly, whether there existed any relationship between dividends payout and Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises in Kenya? Secondly, whether there was a moderating effect of 'a Bird in the Hand' theory on the relationship between dividend payout and Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises in Kenya.

Objectives: The study was guided by the following two objectives;

1. To evaluate the relationship between dividend payout and the Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises in Kenya.
2. To assess the moderating effect of the 'Bird in The Hand' theory on the relationship between dividends payout and Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises in Kenya.

Hypotheses: The study was guided by the following two null hypotheses;

1. There is no significant relationship between dividend payout and the Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises in Kenya.
2. A Bird in Hand theory has no positive significant moderating effect on the relationship between dividend payout and Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises in Kenya.

Literature Review: The study applied the theory of the 'Bird in The Hand' which informed the study variables. The study also reviewed empirical studies on dividend payout decisions and Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises in Kenya. These were compared by the prior studies reviews, in each case, bringing out the gaps that existed.

Theoretical Review: The current study applied the 'Bird in the Hand' theory. The theory was developed by Myron Gordon and John Litner. The theory was based on the fact that investors preferred dividends from stock to potential capital gains (Pandey, 2015).

This was due to the inherent uncertainty associated with capital gains. Based on the adage, the 'Bird in the Hand' is worth two in The Bush. Capital gains investing represented. The two in the bush side of the adage. The theory states that investors prefer the certainty of dividend payments to the possibility of substantially higher future capital gains. As a result, investors require a higher return when companies retain a large fraction of the earnings. This is because investors are risk averse and future capital gains are uncertain. The 'Bird in the Hand' Theory is relevant to the current study in that most MSEs operate on small scales. MSEs

Working capital and assets are limited and their overall turnover is usually small compared to larger enterprises (Mburu, 2012). Due to these facts, it is expected that most MSEs would prefer to be paid their returns at the earliest opportunity possible. This is because they feel insecure with most of their monies tied up in capital which pays back after a long time. They would prefer to be paid even small income out of their investment in dividend stock 'now' than waiting for huge incomes out of their long term capital gains in the future.

Empirical Review: In this section, Past studies on dividend payout decisions and their findings have been compared against the current study. The current study variables for Micro and Small Enterprises included, Investment Income, short term capital gain and diversification.

Investment Income and Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises

Investment Income is income that comes from various sources including; dividends, capital gains collected upon the sale of a security or other assets such as shares, stock and any methods by which businesses or individuals can invest to grow their money. Most MSEs, being risk averse, invest their shares in dividends paying stocks which guarantee a regular flow of income quarterly or within a short period. This is in conformity with the 'Bird in Hand' Theory. Investment income is then reinvested in MSEs business, used to purchase more noncurrent assets or paid to employees as salaries which enhance performance and Growth of MSEs in the short run. Given two mutually exclusive investment projects, MSEs would choose investments that have the shortest payback period.

A study by Aroni, Namusonge and Sakwa (2014) examined the effects of dividend payout on investment in shares for Kenyan retail investors. The study applied behavioural finance theory. Data analysis was conducted applying descriptive and linear regression statistical data analysis. Findings revealed that dividend payout had a significant influence on decisions to invest in shares with p-value .000($p < 0.05$). The study focussed on retail investors who are nonprofessional market participants who generally invest smaller amounts. They are usually less knowledgeable, less disciplined, less skilful and more prone to behavioural and emotional judgement. This explains why the study applied behavioural theory that suited the audience. The current study, on the other hand, addressed the MSEs with having the following characteristics; lower revenue and profitability, smaller terms of employees, sole or partnership form of ownership. Thus a group more enlightened than retail investors. Most of the MSEs are still in their initial stage of business and are looking forward to growing their business. They would rather invest in projects with shorter payback periods; hence the current study's application of 'a Bird in Hand' is worth two in the bush suited the study.

Malik, Khan and Rehman (2019), a study on factors influencing corporate dividend payout decisions of financial and non-financial firms. The results from the probit model estimation revealed that earnings per share, company profitability, and size increase the probability of companies paying a dividend, whereas growth opportunities decrease the probability of paying dividends.

Whereas the past study focused mainly on factors influencing dividend payout of larger firms quoted at the NSE, however, the current study focussed on the relationship of dividend payout and Growth of MDEs with the effects of 'a Bird in Hand' theory. Further the prior studies used earning per share, company profitability, and size and Growth opportunities as their variables. The current study, however, concentrated on different variables including; investments income, capital gains and diversification which are indicators of MSEs Growth.

Short Term Capital gains and Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises

Capital gain is the rise in the value of a capital asset that gives it higher worth than the purchase price. The gain is not realized until the asset is sold. Capital gain may be short term (up to one year) or long term depending on the type of investment. Most MSEs would prefer short term capital gains to long term capital gains. This is due to the fact that the longer an investment takes; the more likely the risks associated with it might go up ranging from economic instability, inflation, government regulations, amongst other factors. This would consequently reduce the value of a firms share. Shareholders wealth will reduce. MSEs would prefer to invest in companies that pay high dividends as this will signal a strong company in the market. The result will be witnessed in higher share prices of its shares and thus maximize shareholders wealth. The final

impact will be higher profits which call for distribution of higher dividends to the shareholders and this will increase the Growth of the MSEs.

Njuguna and Jagongo (2015) the study considered factors that affected dividend payout decisions among listed companies in Kenya. The study established that the current and future profitability of a company, the cash flow position, the financing requirements and the availability of profitable investments were considered in the dividend payout decision of a firm. However, the size of a firm, the number of years of operation (age) and the nature of the industry do not significantly affect a company's dividend policy in relation to payout.

However, some studies did not assess the effects of dividend payout on listed firms and or MSEs Profits. For instance, a study by Murekefu and Ouma (2015) sought to establish the relationship between dividend payout and firm performance among listed firms in the Nairobi Securities Exchange. Regression analysis was carried out to establish the relationship between dividend payout and firm performance. The findings indicated that dividend payout was a major factor affecting firm performance. Their relationship was also strong and positive.

A study by Ntim .et al (2017), assessed corporate governance and dividend pay-out policy in the UK listed SMEs. Findings showed that board size, and audit committee size had a significant relationship with the level of dividend pay-out. However, the frequency of board meetings and board gender diversity had a significant negative relationship with the level of dividend pay-out. The current study used different variables including; Investment income, investment gains and diversification that influenced MSE's growth.

Diversification and Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises

Diversification is the process of a business allocating capital in a way that reduces the exposure to any one particular asset or risk. A common path towards diversification is to reduce risk or volatility by investing in a variety of assets. There is usually a need for diversification in order to create a portfolio balance in investments. A diversified investment is a portfolio of various assets that earns the highest return for the least risk. This is the main aim of MSEs investment decisions as they are mostly risk averse investors.

Diversification includes minimising the risk of loss if one investment performs poorly over a certain period, the other investments may perform better over that same period, reducing the potential losses of the investment portfolio of 'placing all your eggs in one basket'. MSEs should strive to attain a synergetic advantage in their investments where the sums of two or more investments put together are greater than the sum of independent investments.

Numerous studies on the influence of diversifications and firms' performance have been conducted without universal agreements. A study by Park and Jang (2013) investigated the effects of related and unrelated diversification on the performance of restaurant industries in both short and long runs. Findings revealed that restaurant firms do not benefit from the low level of related diversification. The study also established that when restaurant firms are involved in both related and unrelated businesses, the optimum mixed ratio of diversification is approximately half to half.

The study concentrated on related and unrelated diversification of restaurant businesses only. However, the effects of MSEs Growth based on diversification in stock dividends were lacking.

Santarelli and Tran's (2015) study on diversification strategies and firm performance in Vietnam was based on the assumption that a firm's profitability is determined by its degree of diversification. The result indicated that diversification had a curvilinear effect on profitability. This meant that it improved a firm's profit up to a point after which a further increase in diversification was associated with declining profitability. The study focused on the degree of diversification on a firm's profitability. This contrasted sharply with the current study which focussed was on the role played by diversification on MSEs Growth with respect to dividend payout and investment in shares.

Bachtiar (2020), a study on stages appropriate for SMEs to diversify utilizing the growth stage model. Using Threat, Opportunity, Weaknesses and Strength (TOWS) analysis the study established that despite the fact that diversification is important for the growth of SMEs, it could not be undertaken in stages one and two of their Growth. Whereas the prior study measured its variables based on TOWS, the current study adopted a

Bird in Hand model. None the less, most MSEs are in their first and second stages of Growth, could these findings be replicated into the current study?

A study by Wanyonyi (2018), examined the effect of investment diversification on the financial performance of manufacturing firms listed at the NSE. Findings revealed that diversification explained 52.8% of firms’ financial performance. The study also found that horizontal, concentric, conglomerate and vertical diversifications had a positive relationship with the financial performance of listed manufacturing firms. The study concentrated on the influence of diversification on the financial performance of listed firms. However, the current study’s focus was on dividend payout on investment in shares leading to MSEs Growth. The current study assessed the effect of diversification on MSEs Growth.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework shows the direct and moderating relationships that exist between the variables and the independent variable. Dividend payout is used as an independent variable; A Bird in hand theory has been used as a moderating variable and MSEs growth (Investment in shares) as a dependent variable.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Authors Conceptualisation

Methodology: The study adopted an ex- post facto and cross-sectional research design. A cross- sectional design since data was collected only once from MSEs spread within Nairobi Central District An ex-post facto design assesses the relationship between dividend payout and Growth of MSEs The design was ideal for conducting social science research when it is not possible to manipulate the characteristics of human participants (Tunji, 2012). The study relied heavily on primary data since data was collected from 100 Micro and Small Enterprises business owners through questionnaires. The 100 Micro and Small Enterprises business owners were randomly selected from the Nairobi Central Business District (CBD). Nairobi (CBD) is Kenya’s epicentre of business thus many MSEs are located there.

Data analysis and interpretation

The study had a 90% response rate, 90 questionnaires were returned for analysis.

Table 1.1: Model summaries for dividend pay-out and investment in shares of Micro Small Enterprises in Kenya

Regression model				Statistic	Value	
Logistic regression				Number of obs	=	90
				LR chi2 (8)	=	14.067
				Prob> chi2	=	0.0315
Log likelihood = -181.734				Pseudo R2	=	0.465
	Coeff.	Std. Err.	Z	P>z	[95% Conf.	Interval]
Dividend pay-out	0.252	0.178	2.042	0.025	0.016	0.578
_const.	-0.859	0.149	-6.46	0	-1.215	-0.654

The summary statistics are divided into two sections: the goodness of the fit section and the coefficient section. In the goodness-of-fit part, we see LR Chi2 = 14.067 with a p-value of 0.0315. Chi2 value and its p-value are used to check for the significance of the model fit. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the Chi2 value implies that the model is significant and adequately fits the data. That is, the model is a significant fit than a model with no predictor(s), an empty model.

The Pseudo R2 value is used to check for the extent to which the independent variable(s) influences the dependent variable. Therefore, the value of the Pseudo R2 = 0.465 implies that variations in the independent variable (Dividend pay-out) only account for 46.5% of the total variations in the log likelihood of investment in shares of Micro Small Enterprises. This means that the remaining 53.5% of the variation is accounted for by factors not explained by or included in the model.

In the coefficient section, we have coefficients for each of the predictor variables with the corresponding standard errors, z-statistics, p-values and the 95% confidence intervals. Summary statistics for this section shows that the coefficient of Dividend pay-out was 0.252, and that of the constant coefficient was -0.859. Based on these coefficient values, we obtained the following logistic regression equation

$$\text{Log}_e \left(\frac{P(Y)}{1 - P(Y)} \right) = -0.859 + 0.252X$$

To test for the effect of Dividend pay-out, of importance is the coefficient value for Dividend pay-outs. From Table, the Z statistic of the coefficient of Dividend pay-out was found to be 2.042 with a corresponding p-value 0.025 (< 0.05). Based on the obtained p-value, the coefficient was considered to be significant at 0.05 level of significance.

This means that any improvement in the aspects of Dividend pay-out by one unit would increase the log odds of investment in shares, by 0.252. From the coefficient of Dividend pay-out, the odds ratio of performing in the job market corresponds to a unit increase in the level of Dividend pay-out which is given by $e^{0.252} = 1.286$.

Since the p-value was less than 0.05, we inferred that there is a significant proportional change in the odds of investment in shares by 1.286 due to a unit increase in the levels of Dividend pay-out. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the study rejected the null hypothesis H_{01} at a 5% level of significance about the non-significance of the effect of Dividend pay-out on the investment in shares of Micro and Small Enterprises in Kenya. This decision implied that Dividend pay-out has a significant influence on the investment in shares of Micro and Small Enterprises in Kenya.

TABLE 1.2 Model Summaries for Moderating Effect of Bird in Hand Theory

Information Criterion Change Statistics						
Block	LL	LR	Df	Pr>LR	AIC	BIC
1	-181.293	12.473	2	0.006	368.586	379.843
2	-177.524	7.533	1	0.013	363.051	378.061
Coefficients for Moderation Effect of Bird in Hand Theory						
	Coeff.	Std. Err.	Z	P>z	[95% Conf.	Interval]
Dividend pay-out	0.42	0.187	2.135	0.022	0.031	0.729
Bird in Hand Theory	0.643	0.239	2.627	0.010	0.134	0.922
Interaction Variable	-0.475	0.24	-1.979	0.017	-0.945	-0.005
_const.	-0.921	0.135	-6.833	0.000	-1.186	-0.656

In the Table, the study has the likelihood ratio change due to the addition of the interaction variable. The significance of this change is tested by the p-value in the Block 2 model.

From the Table, the study observed that the change in the LR due to the addition of the interaction variable is significant as shown by the P-value (= 0.013), which is less than 0.05.

This confirmed that the addition of the interaction variable significantly improved the model at a 5% significance level. In the coefficients' section, we have the coefficients for Dividend pay-out, Bird in Hand Theory and the interaction variable. Both Dividend pay-out and Bird in Hand Theory were significant since their respective p-values, 0.022 and 0.010, were significant at a 5% level of significance. Of interest was, however, the significance of the added interaction variable. From the output, the study observed that the interaction variables were significant at a 5% significance level since the corresponding p-value = 0.017 was less than 0.05.

Based on the significances of both likelihood ratio changes and the interaction variable, the study rejected the null hypothesis H_{02} . Bird in Hand Theory had no significant moderating effect on the relationship between Dividend pay-out and Growth of MSEs in the Kenyan economy. The study therefore, concluded that Bird in Hand Theory had a significant moderating effect on the relationship between Dividend pay-out and investment in shares of Micro and Small Enterprises in Kenya.

Findings and Discussions: The first objective of the study was to evaluate the relationship between dividend payout and Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises in Kenya. The study established that there was a significant positive relationship between dividend payout and the Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises in Kenya. This finding established that when MSEs invest in a stock paying dividends, they earn income from their investments. Secondly, stock dividends are usually reinvested back to the firm which facilitates Growth of the MSEs. A study by Murekefu and Ouma (2015) concurs; the findings indicated that dividend payout was a major factor affecting firm performance and that their relationship was also strong and positive. Findings by Yegon and Sang (2014) are in agreement, it indicated a significant positive relationship between dividend policies of organizations and the firm's profitability, a significant positive relationship between dividend policy and investments and a significant positive relationship between dividend policy and Earnings per Share. Findings by Malik, Gul and Rehman (2019), revealed that earnings per share, company profitability, and size increase the probability of companies to pay a dividend, whereas growth opportunities decrease the probability of paying dividends.

However, some studies found contradicting results, for instance, Njuguna and Jagongo (2015) established that the size of a firm, the number of years of operation (age) and the nature of the industry do not significantly affect a company's dividend policy in relation to payout. This contradicts the findings of the

current study that MSEs being in their first and second state of Growth and also having a relatively smaller size than most large firms listed at the security Exchange would want to earn a return in their investment in the shortest period possible to facilitate their Growth.

The second objective of the study was to analyse the moderating effect of 'a Bird in Hand' theory on the relationship between dividends payout and investment in shares leading to the Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises in Kenya. Finding revealed that 'A Bird in Hand' theory has a positive significant moderating effect on the relationship between dividend payout and investment in shares leading to the Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises in Kenya. This finding implies that most MSEs are in their first or second stage of Growth and thus are interested in investing in dividends that have the shortest pay back periods. This is due to the fact that they are risk averse and would want an investment that has the highest return with minimum risks. This is only achievable by investing in stock dividends. The finding is thus in agreement by 'a Bird in hand is worth two in the bush' theory. Investing in capital gains would take a long time to pay back with a future that is uncertain especially to MSEs.

The finding of the study is consistent with that established by Bachtiar (2020) established that diversification is not possible by firms which are in their first and second stage of Growth. According to the findings, only larger firms that have accumulated funds have the capabilities of venturing into diversification, unlike MSEs which require returns in the short run. Further, most MSEs do not have enough funds to venture into diversification. However, findings by Santarelli and Tran (2015), reported contradicting results which indicated that diversification had a curvilinear effect on profitability. It acted as the Economics law of Diminishing Marginal Utility.

This meant that it improved a firm's profit up to a point after which a further increase in diversification was associated with declining profitability.

Limitations, Justifications and Suggestions for Future Researchers

Contextual limitation; the study was limited to MSEs Business within Nairobi County. This was due to the limited time within which the study was conducted and also given that MSEs are the major employers in Kenya and it was not possible to address all of them. However, MSEs selected were a good representation in Kenya given that Nairobi has the largest number of these businesses. This did not affect the quality of the study. Future researchers should consider addressing MSEs Spread within all Kenya's regions.

Conceptual limitation; the study's variables were investment income, investment gains and diversification which were used as factors influencing dividend payout on investment in shares leading to MSEs Growth. Other factors such as earnings per share, dividends per share, political stability, government regulations, among others could have been used. However, this did not compromise the quality of the study.

Theoretical limitation; the study applied 'a Bird in Hand' theory to address the behaviour of MSEs towards investment in stock dividends. This was so as MSEs Investors believed that the theory was based on accelerated their Growth. Future researchers should consider using other dividend theories such as Modigliani and Miller's theory, signalling theory, among others.

Methodological limitation; the study applied descriptive, ex post factor and cross sectional research design. Ex post factor design was used to assess the relationship between dividend payout on investment of shares leading to MSEs Growth. Cross sectional design was applied as data was collected by the use of a questionnaire at once and response obtained from the MSEs. Data were analysed using logistic regression since the study was binary and dichotomous in nature. However, future researchers should consider other statistical methodologies such as longitudinal research design and analyse data using co - relational. It is worth to note despite the use of the aforesaid methodology, the quality of research was not compromised.

Contribution to the body of Knowledge: contrary to the general belief that MSEs are not interested in investing in dividend stocks, the current study's inclusion of the 'Bird in the Hand' theory has brought a lot of insights and encouragement to MSEs to invest in a stock paying dividends. Since most of the MSEs

are in their early stages of Growth, investing in stock dividends is a bird in hand which is worth two birds in the bush. The good news which the study has for all MSEs is that if they invest in dividend stocks, they will be paid in terms of stock or cash depending on their choices. Further, given many challenges that are facing most MSEs and their negative perceptions towards investments, this study would act as 'a wakeup call' to them. To the Government of Kenya, since MSEs are the economy's major employer, this study would be 'food for thought.' And thus a 'turning point' for the Government of Kenya to support MSEs businesses financially, politically and to also encourage them to invest in dividend stocks for their faster Growth.

Conclusion: Based on the study's discussions, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Dividend payout affects the Growth of MSEs and that this relationship is strong and positive. It therefore shows that investments in dividend stocks are relevant and therefore affect the Growth of MSEs especially when it is begged on the 'Bird in The Hand' theory that recognizes the fact that little money now is worth more than a lot of money in the uncertain future.
2. The study contradicted sharply other dividend irrelevant theories that advocate the opposite. For instance MM dividend theory states that the dividend policy of a firm has no effect on its value and the stock price hence does not influence a firm's Growth.
3. The study observed a new phenomenon that investments in dividend stocks by MSEs influence their Growth. This is due to the fact that cash dividends were the most commonly used form of a dividend by MSEs in Kenya. Other factors that were established to largely influencing MSEs Growth through dividend payout were investment income, dividend gains and diversification.

References

- i. Aroni, J., Namusonge, G., & Sakwa, M. (2014). *Influence of Dividend Payout on Investment in Shares- A Survey of Retail Investors. International Journal of Business and Social Science, 155-163.*
- ii. Bachtiar, N. K. (2020). *When can SMEs Diversify? A study of Growth Stage Model Analysis. Journal of Economics ,Business and Management, 30-37.*
- iii. Finke, M., Huston, S., & Winchester, D. (2011). *Financial Advice: Who Pays. Journal of Financial Counselling and Planning, 18-26.*
- iv. Gveroski, M., & Risteska, A. (2017). *Determinants of Investment Decisions in SMEs. Balkan and Near Eastern Journal of Social Sciences, 71-78.*
- v. Malik, F., Khan, M. T., & Rehman, S. (2013). *Factors Influencing Corporate Dividend Payout Decisions on Financial and Non-financial Firms . Research Journal of Finance and Accounting, 35-46.*
- vi. Mburu, S. (2012). *Factors that cause the failure of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Kenya. Kenyaplex.*
- vii. Modigliani, F., & Miller, M. (1958, June). *The Cost of Capital, Corporation Finance and the Theory of Investment. The American Economic Review, 48(3), 261-297.*
- viii. Murekefu, T., & Ouma, P. (2015). *The Relationship between Dividend Payout and Firm Performance: A study of Listed Companies in Kenya. European Scientific Journal, 8(9), 199-215.*
- ix. Njuguna, I., & Jagongo, A. (2015). *Factors Considered in Dividend Payout Decisions- The Case for Listed Companies in Kenya. Research Journal of Finance and Accounting, 68-74.*
- x. Ntim, E., Malagila, Fosu, Crossley, Samuel, Vu, . . . G., C. (2017). *Corporate Governance and dividend pay-out policy in UK listed SMEs: The effects of corporate board characteristics. International Journal of Accounting and Information Management., 459-483.*

- xi. Otengo, M. A. (2016). Factors influencing the use of business advisory services of micro and small enterprises in Nairobi city council, Kenya. Phd Thesis.*
- xii. Pandey, I. M. (2015). Financial Management. New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House.*
- xiii. Santareli, E., & Tran, H. (2015). Diversification strategies and Firm Performance in Vietnam. Economics of Transition, 31-68.*
- xiv. Tunji, S. T. (2012). Accounting Information as an aid to management decision making. International Journal of Management and Social Sciences Research.*
- xv. Wanyonyi, R. N. (2018). Effect of Investment Diversification on Financial Performance of Agricultural Firms Listed at Nairobi Securities Exchange Kenya. International Journal of Finance and Accounting, 3(8).*